

How does CESSDA implement the TRUST principles?

Long before the formalisation of the TRUST principles, CESSDA had already embedded Transparency, Responsibility, User Focus, Sustainability, and Technology into its governance and operational models. By endorsing these principles, CESSDA ensures that research data is managed ethically and securely for the long-term benefit of society.

Transparency

refers to clear public documentation of repository policies, governance, and service conditions.

- ✓ Public documentation
- ✓ International certification
- ✓ Performance assessment

Responsibility

involves stewardship of the data holdings and ensures compliance with legal, ethical, and professional standards.

- ✓ Data stewardship
- ✓ Metadata and curation standards
- ✓ Compliance with EU regulations

User focus

means supporting a wide user community to use and reuse research data.

- ✓ User-centric digital tools
- ✓ Training and outreach
- ✓ User engagement

Sustainability

refers to long-term repository viability through stable funding, expertise, and infrastructure maintenance.

- ✓ European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC)
- ✓ Community knowledge sharing
- ✓ Strategy and coordination

Technology

is about using robust, interoperable, and secure systems for data management, preservation, and access.

- ✓ Metadata standards and reliable services
- ✓ Training and outreach
- ✓ Secure infrastructure and services

What are the key practices?

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- ✓ Publish scientific policies (e.g., on persistent identifiers and data access), statutes, strategy, annual reports, and service descriptions.
- ✓ Promote CoreTrustSeal, an international certification of trustworthy repositories, and transparent repository practices.
- ✓ Report annual key performance indicators aligned with ESFRI objectives.

R

- ✓ Provide stewardship through data citation guidance and common policies across the data lifecycle.
- ✓ Adhere to international standards, including DDI and OAIS.
- ✓ Protect intellectual property rights and ensure compliance with EU regulations, including GDPR, EU AI Act, and Digital Services Act.

U

- ✓ Offer tools to support users throughout the data lifecycle, including the Data Catalogue, Resource Directory, and Vocabulary Service.
- ✓ Deliver webinars and workshops, and provide advisory input on Open Science (e.g., EOSC).
- ✓ Collect user feedback to improve services and data practices.

S

- ✓ Ensure long-term sustainability through ERIC governance and Service Providers' commitment.
- ✓ Foster collaboration through working groups, external networks, and the Trust Support Programme.
- ✓ Maintain long-term data access through strategic planning and oversight by its General Assembly and Service Providers' Forum.

T

- ✓ Implement the CESSDA Metadata Model and contribute to standards, e.g., DDI.
- ✓ Maintain a technical roadmap to address cybersecurity and risks related to platform innovation and AI adoption.

Learn more:

- Lin, D., Crabtree, J., Dillo, I. et al. (2020). The TRUST Principles for digital repositories. *Scientific Data* 7 (144). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-020-0486-7>
- Kleemola, M., & Wong, L. (2025). *The battle for trust: Advancing the social science data ecosystem*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15125538>

T – Transparency

- ESFRI refers to the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures.
- CESSDA ERIC. (n.d.). *Documents and policies*. CESSDA. <https://www.cessda.eu/About/Documents-and-Policies>
- CoreTrustSeal. (n.d.). *CoreTrustSeal*. <https://www.coretrustseal.org/>
- CESSDA ERIC. (2025). *Measuring what matters: Progress across CESSDA 2020–2024*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17855452>

R – Responsibility

- DDI refers to the Data Documentation Initiative. OAIS refers to the Open Archival Information System. GDPR is the General Data Protection Regulation.
- CESSDA ERIC. (2025). *Data Citation Guide*. CESSDA. <https://datacitation.cessda.eu/>
- CESSDA ERIC. (n.d.). *Metadata Validator*. CESSDA. <https://www.cessda.eu/Tools/Metadata-Validator>
- CESSDA ERIC. (n.d.). *Data Archiving Guide*. CESSDA. <https://dag.cessda.eu/>

U – User Focus

- EOSC refers to the European Open Science Cloud.
- CESSDA ERIC. (n.d.). *Tools*. CESSDA. <https://www.cessda.eu/Tools>
- CESSDA ERIC. (n.d.). *Training*. CESSDA. <https://www.cessda.eu/Training>
- CESSDA ERIC. (n.d.). *CESSDA and Researchers*. CESSDA. <https://www.cessda.eu/Development-Impact/CESSDA-and-Researchers>

S – Sustainability

- CESSDA ERIC. (n.d.). *Statutes*. CESSDA. <https://www.cessda.eu/About/Governance/Statutes>
- Kleemola, M., Verburg, M., Wong, L. et al. (2026). *CESSDA Trust Support: a Peer-Driven Multi-Way Process* [Conference poster]. 20th International Digital Curation Conference, Zagreb. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18843403>
- CESSDA ERIC. (n.d.). *Governance*. CESSDA. <https://www.cessda.eu/About/Governance>

T – Technology

- Akdeniz, E., & Moilanen, K. (2023). *CMM CESSDA Metadata Model (3.0)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7528240>

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20281957>

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